

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Figure 3.5 Network diagram illustrating the extent of knowledge on indirect (blue circles), direct (green circles) drivers of biodiversity change and natural drivers (grey circle), and their interactions

Version: 1

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7861124

Project leader and contributor:

- Philip E. Hulme
- Tanara Renard Truong

Description

Network diagram illustrates the extent of knowledge on indirect (blue circles), direct (green circles) drivers of biodiversity change and natural drivers (grey circle), and their interactions. The thickness of the lines between drivers is indicative of the number of papers that jointly addressed the two linked drivers. The size of the stroke of each circle reflects the number of papers on a particular driver in relation to invasive alien species.

Process overview

Number of publications are searched on the Web of Science by a particular driver in relation to invasive alien species. Then a network diagram is developed with thickness of lines and size of stroke of each circle reflecting the result of the search.

Protocol

The thickness of the lines between drivers is indicative of the number of papers that jointly addressed the two linked drivers ("Node_S" or "Node_T" column).

The size of the stroke of each circle reflects the number of papers listed by Web of Science between 2000 and 2019 generated by a topic search on a particular driver in relation to invasive alien species ("Weight" and "stroke" column).

Note the greater emphasis on direct drivers both individually and jointly.

Note that effects of biodiversity loss on biological invasions are not included in this figure.

Code for drivers in the dataset: CLM (climate change), RES (natural resource extraction), POL (pollution), LND (land- and sea-use changes), IAS (invasive alien species), NAT (natural drivers), SOC (sociocultural

drivers and social values), DEM (demographic drivers), ECO (economic drivers), TEC (science and technology), GOV (policies, governance and institutions).

Abbreviation used in the dataset: Source (Abbreviated source node name), Target (Abbreviated target node name), Weight (Edge weight (number of publications)), Node_S (Source node attribute (total publications on that driver)), Node_T (Target node attribute (total publications on that driver)), SourceFull (Full source node name), TargetFull (Full target node name)